

Dynamics of oceanic slab tearing during transform-fault oblique subduction: Insights from 3D numerical modeling

Jie Xin¹, Huai Zhang^{1,*}, Zhong-Hai Li¹, Felipe Orellana-Rovirosa², Liang Liu³,
Yigang Xu³, Zhen Zhang¹, Yaolin Shi¹

¹Key Laboratory of Computational Geodynamics, College of Earth and Planetary
Sciences, University of Chinese Academy of Sciences, Beijing 100049, China

²Department of Ocean Science and Engineering, Southern University of Science and
Technology, Shenzhen 518055, China

³State Key Laboratory of Isotope Geochemistry, Guangzhou Institute of Geochemistry,
Chinese Academy of Sciences, Guangzhou 510640, China

*Corresponding: <hzhang@ucas.ac.cn>

1. Dataset of tearing width of different stages in Figure 4, 5

Original data/ tearing width-stage.xlsx

2. Dataset of all the models' tearing width in Figure 6-9

Original data/ tearing width.xlsx

Original data/ tearing width-controlling factors.xlsx

3. Dataset of the models and plugin

Reference model (3327_20) input file: Model_plugin/3327_20.prm

All model setups: Model_plugin/ model setup.xlsx

Initial composition plugin and Initial temperature plugin:

Model_plugin/*.cpp,

Model_plugin/*.h

You can refer to section 6.2 of the ASPECT manual to use the plugin.

<https://github.com/geodynamics/aspect/releases/tag/v2.3.0>

4. Dataset of obliqueness angle and seafloor age in Figure 1

Figure 1/angle,

Figure 1/age,

GMT Script: Figure 1/run.sh